

Non-equilibrium growth patterns and kinetic studies during electrodeposition of metals from $\text{CuSO}_4\text{-ZnSO}_4$ solutions

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2D Electrodeposits from aqueous solutions of copper sulfate, zinc sulfate and mixture of copper sulfate-zinc sulfate in different proportions and experimental conditions have been investigated. Morphology of deposits from $\text{CuSO}_4 + \text{ZnSO}_4$ solutions shows mixed cauliflower structure and dendritic structure characteristic of copper and zinc, respectively. The results show that deposits are not homogeneous. Growth kinetic studies and cathode potential changes during electrodeposition indicate approximately regular behaviour during the growth of electrodeposit. Results have been explained on the basis of model suggested by Trigueros *et al.*

Morphological studies of a wide variety of electrodeposits, dendritic and DLA like fractal patterns under various conditions have evoked considerable interest during recent years¹ on account of the need for a deeper understanding of similar type of non-equilibrium structures in bacterial growth², fungal growth³ and crystal growth⁴. It has been shown that morphology of electrodeposits depends on a number of parameters including ion concentration, applied potential difference, cell thickness and electrode separation^{5,6}. Recently, the influence of an inert electrolyte, e.g. Na_2SO_4 on electrodeposition of copper from copper sulfate solution has been investigated by Trigueros *et al.*⁶. It was thought of interest to investigate morphological features of electrodeposits from mixtures of solutions of electrolytes. For this purpose, mixture of CuSO_4 and ZnSO_4 was chosen for detailed study.

Normally, codeposition of Cu and Zn from such solutions of CuSO_4 and ZnSO_4 is not expected in view of (i) considerable difference in discharge potential of Cu and Zn and (ii) absolutely no possibility of exceeding the critical current density of Cu by Zn during the electrodeposition. However, codeposition is possible if fractal growth of DLA type occurs then the concentration of Cu^{II} ion in the crevices can become negligible. Thus facilitating codeposition of Zn^{II} . Such a situation has also been postulated by Trigueros *et al.*⁶ for electrodeposition from CuSO_4 and Na_2SO_4 solutions. The present investigation was therefore undertaken to test the above hypothesis and examine the development of growth of such patterns in binary mixtures of active cations.

Results and Discussion

The microphotographs of electrodeposits obtained from CuSO_4 , $\text{CuSO}_4 + \text{ZnSO}_4$ solutions in different proportions and ZnSO_4 were recorded. Characteristic patterns were obtained for deposits from pure CuSO_4 and ZnSO_4 solutions (0.1 M) but the patterns of the same at lower concentration (0.01 M) were more compact. Electrodeposit of $\text{CuSO}_4\text{-ZnSO}_4$ binary system [CuSO_4] = 0.050 M, [ZnSO_4] = 0.050 M was found to be interesting in the sense that visual observations indicated yellow colour resembling β -brass. SEM photographs of electrodeposits for Cu and Zn clearly display the cauliflower and dendritic structure, respectively, similar to that as observed by Grier *et al.*⁷. As the concentration of Cu increases in the deposit, the cauliflower component increases. But the deposits are not homogeneous as ESCA studies reveal. Studies on composition of electrodeposits by atomic absorption spectroscopy reveal that it is not much different from the solution used for electrodeposition.

Figs. 1 and 2 show growth behaviour of electrodeposited aggregates obtained from pure CuSO_4 , ZnSO_4 and mixture of CuSO_4 and ZnSO_4 in different proportions using a vertical point cathode surrounded by circular anode. The growth rate was found to increase with increase in copper ion concentration in the solution. The data recorded in Fig. 1 obey the simple equation, $d^2 = kt + c$, where d is the radius of the circular envelope of the aggregate, measured from the point cathode at any time t and c is the intercept. The values of correlation coefficient are very close to 1. The slope (m) was found to increase with

Fig. 1. Plots of d vs t showing growth kinetics of electrodeposited clusters obtained from aqueous solutions of (i) CuSO_4 (0.1 M); (ii) ZnSO_4 (0.1 M), binary system containing CuSO_4 and ZnSO_4 in different proportions; (iii) $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}] = 0.066 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}] = 0.033 \text{ M}$; (iv) $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}] = 0.050 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}] = 0.050 \text{ M}$; (v) $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}] = 0.033 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}] = 0.066 \text{ M}$, employing circular anode and vertical cathode; field intensity = 5.36 V cm^{-1} .

increase in $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}]$. Growth kinetics of electrodeposition from aqueous solution containing CuSO_4 (0.1 M) and ZnSO_4 (0.1 M) mixed in equal volume were studied employing two parallel electrodes at different field intensities. The results show fairly good straight-lines when the values of d are plotted against time t as evident by the correlation coefficient values. The values of slope m indicate that the growth rate increases with increase in field intensity.

Cathode potential changes with time were noted during the process of electrodeposition. Figs. 3 and 4 show the potential changes with time during the electrodeposition from aqueous copper sulfate, zinc sulfate and copper sulfate admixed with zinc sulfate in different proportions.

Fig. 2. Growth kinetics of electrodeposited clusters obtained from aqueous solutions of (i) CuSO_4 (0.003 M); (ii) ZnSO_4 (0.003 M), binary system containing CuSO_4 and ZnSO_4 in different proportions; (iii) $[\text{CuSO}_4] = 0.002 \text{ M}$, $[\text{ZnSO}_4] = 0.001 \text{ M}$; (iv) $[\text{CuSO}_4] = 0.0015 \text{ M}$, $[\text{ZnSO}_4] = 0.0015 \text{ M}$; (v) $[\text{CuSO}_4] = 0.001 \text{ M}$, $[\text{ZnSO}_4] = 0.002 \text{ M}$, employing circular anode and vertical cathode; field intensity = 7.10 V cm^{-1} .

Thus the experimental results show that electrodeposition of both Cu and Zn occurs from $\text{CuSO}_4 + \text{ZnSO}_4$ solution under the given experimental condition as revealed by SEM and atomic absorption spectroscopy. The deposits are not homogeneous as indicated by ESCA. However, the growth kinetic and cathode potential changes indicate that the process of electrodeposition is not chaotic.

Fig. 3. Cathode potential changes with time during electrodeposition of metals from aqueous solutions of (i) CuSO_4 (0.1 M); (ii) ZnSO_4 (0.1 M), binary system containing CuSO_4 and ZnSO_4 in different proportions; (iii) $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}] = 0.066 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}] = 0.033 \text{ M}$; (iv) $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}] = 0.050 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}] = 0.050 \text{ M}$; (v) $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}] = 0.033 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}] = 0.066 \text{ M}$; field intensity = 3.08 V cm^{-1} .

Fig. 4. Cathode potential changes with time during electrodeposition of metals from aqueous solutions of (i) CuSO_4 (0.01 M); (ii) ZnSO_4 (0.01 M), binary system containing CuSO_4 and ZnSO_4 in different proportions; (iii) $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}] = 0.0066 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}] = 0.0033 \text{ M}$; (iv) $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}] = 0.0050 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}] = 0.0066 \text{ M}$; (v) $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}] = 0.0033 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}] = 0.0066 \text{ M}$; field intensity = 3.08 V cm^{-1} .

In the context of codeposition of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} it may be noted that in case of Cu-Zn system, metal radii of Cu and Zn are 1.28 and 1.38 Å, respectively. Five different phases α , β , γ , ϵ and η have been distinguished. In phase α (0–35% Zn) random substitutional solution of Zn in Cu is observed and in case of β (45–50% Zn) inter-metallic compounds of approximate stoichiometry is found. On the other hand, for γ (60–65% Zn) and ϵ (82–86% Zn) phases inter-metallic compounds of stoichiometry Cu_5Zn_8 and CuZn_3 are formed, respectively. Random substitutional solid solution of Cu in Zn is formed in η phase (97–100% Zn)⁸.

The codeposition can be understood in terms of the model used by Trigueros *et al.*⁶ for explaining experimental results for deposition from copper sulfate solution with small amount of Na_2SO_4 . The model assumes that no current flows though the solution between the branches of the deposit, so that the concentration of the electroactive cation is zero behind the growing front. A similar situation seems to arise in the present case also. The concentration of copper ions in the crevices in the fractal deposit may be reduced to such an extent that limiting current density of Cu^{II} ions in the crevices is exceeded in the fractal deposit. When this happens, deposition of copper will not occur but the deposition of Zn would occur in the neighbourhood. The concentration of zinc ions in due course also goes down and the concentration of Cu^{II} would again build up due to diffusion so that deposition of copper ions again occurs⁹. Development of a quantitative theory based on the above model may have difficulties since the growth velocity of copper and zinc ions are not likely to be the same.

Experimental

Zinc sulfate (G.R., S. Merck) and copper sulfate (A.R., Qualigens) were used as such.

Electrodeposition of metals : 2D-electrodeposits were grown by using two vertical platinum electrodes (99.99%, average dia. 0.5 mm). The distance between two electrodes was kept constant (4.0 cm). Aggregates were grown at the cathode by imposing a constant potential with a DC supply. The electrolyte solutions were prepared with reagent grade chemicals in double-distilled water. The experiments were performed at room temperature ($30 \pm 1^\circ$). Different types of growth morphologies were obtained from aqueous solution of CuSO_4 (0.1 M) and ZnSO_4 (0.1 M) as well as the binary mixture of CuSO_4 and ZnSO_4 in different proportions. No hydrogen evolution during the electrodeposition could be observed. Microphotographs were taken with a Pentax camera.

Characterization of electrodeposits : The electrodeposits were characterized by using atomic absorption spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy and electron spectroscopy for chemical analysis (ESCA). Metals were analysed with a Perkin-Elmer AAS-5000 atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The SEM photographs were taken with the help of a Joel 840 microscope. ESCA studies were carried out with a VG Scientific Mark II ESCA spectrometer and the spectra were recorded by using $\text{MgK}\alpha$ radiation.

Growth kinetics : To study the growth kinetics, two types of electrodes were used as shown in Fig. 5 : (a) circular anode-vertical point cathode, and (b) two identical horizontal electrodes. Growth kinetics of the electrodeposits were studied by noting d , the radius of the circular envelope emerging from the tip of point cathode (in case of circular anode-vertical point cathode). The envelope remained attached to the tip during electrodeposition. In case of parallel electrodes, the length of the tip from the horizontal cathode was measured as a function of time

Fig. 5. Experimental setup of electrodeposition of metals with (a) circular anode-vertical point cathode, and (b) two parallel electrodes; A and C at 4 cm apart, B = DC battery, R = rheostat and M = digital multimeter.

using a travelling microscope. Experiments were carried out at different electrolyte concentrations and in different proportions in case of binary system. Dependence of field intensity on growth kinetics was studied with two parallel electrodes.

Cathode potential changes during electrodeposition of metals : To monitor cathode potential changes with time, two vertical point electrodes and a calomel electrode were employed as described earlier¹. Potential measurements were carried out using a HIL 2101 multimeter accurate to ± 0.01 V. The experiment was conducted in a flat bottom Corning petridish containing 45 ml solution. A glass plate (5 cm \times 5 cm) was put over glass pieces in a dish containing electrolyte solution. Two identical platinum electrodes (4.0 cm apart) were put in the solution. The anode was extended below the surface of the solution while the lower end of the cathode was put at the surface of the solution. A calomel electrode was dipped in the solution. Potential

changes during electrodeposition was monitored with the help of platinum electrodes coupled with a calomel electrode. All experiments were repeated three times and reproducible results were obtained.

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